

● REPORT

Care as a Principle for Urban Public Space

SÖDERTÖRN UNIVERSITY, Stockholm
Department for Environment, Development and Sustainability
Studies, 2025

Romina Rodela, Miriam Williams, Qian Zhang, Madeleine Bonow

RIKSBANKENS
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Department for Environment, Development and Sustainability Studies, Södertörn University

Typology of Care-informed Planning Practice

Governance e.g	Built-form interventions e.g	Participation Processes e.g	Resourcing e.g	Values/Cultures of care:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Frameworks, design guides and guidelines • Charters e.g. London Charter, NSW Public Spaces Charter • Regulations e.g. Environmental Planning Instruments • Taxation regimes • Laws and rights • Gender Impact Assessments • Time Declarations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accessible and Intergenerational design • Heritage preservation • Cultural safety through design • Equitable provisioning • Micro and macro scale e.g. park benches, social housing estates • Community spaces • Responsive to place-based need 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Child friendly cities e.g. Ergler et al (2022) • Planning with preschoolers • Participatory budgeting processes • Democratic and genuine engagement • Data Sovereignty • Enabling community-led activities • Urban Activism 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct provisioning of care infrastructures e.g. public housing, welfare support, • Universal Basic Income • Building "care in" (e.g. Sandstrom, 2019, 2020 work on public space) • Government funding • Public Social partnerships 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relationality • Interdependence between human and non-human worlds • Collective Responsibility • Collective wellbeing • Grounded/ Place-based • Universal need for care • Values carers and care work • Inclusive • Equity • Rights

KEY QUESTIONS: Whose values? Who benefits? Whose needs are met? Is it equitable? Is it just?

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1. Introduction

In recent years, Sweden's urban landscapes have been shaped by growing spatial segregation, densification, and reduced safety (Malmberg et al., 2018). Young people, young families and elderly residents are social groups deeply reliant on accessible, inclusive, and safe public spaces. However they are often the ones most affected by these processes (Sandström, 2020). In many neighbourhoods, public spaces are increasingly commercialised, appear fragmented, or are designed with an emphasis on economic aspects which leads to everyday social needs being undervalued (Listerborn et al. 2020). Meanwhile, the challenges of loneliness among the elderly and the need for community-supportive environments for young people are emerging as a much-needed points of attention in Swedish society (Drozdowski et al., 2021; Webster et al., 2025)

Against this backdrop, and building on our earlier work on care-informed planning, we held a workshop on May 9th, 2025, at Södertörn University. The core objective for the day was to imagine how the urban governance and spatial planning of public spaces would differ if shaped by an Ethics of Care framework and discuss how care could be a guiding principle for public space design and management.

In this, we position care not as an individual, or private matter, but as a human and public activity that is a collective and political responsibility (Power and Williams, 2020; Williams 2020; Rodela et al 2025). This perspective calls for the recognition of the interdependence and vulnerability of all individuals and considering how these, along with contextual factors, constitute essential dimensions of urban life. These dimensions should be integral to the way we design and govern our cities.

Applying a relational Ethics of Care to urban public spaces challenges dominant planning models that prioritize economic growth, mobility flows, and privatization. Instead, it asks: how can cities sustain and nurture life, especially for those who depend most on supportive environments? How can governance and planning practices centre relational needs, such as safety, belonging, dignity, and participation rather than treating care as an afterthought?

We believe the theme is timely and it responds to current policy debates in Sweden about urban inequalities and the role municipal authorities have in urban governance and in shaping more inclusive cities. Through group work and speculative exercises, participants explored how a care-centred approach might

transform public spaces in Swedish periphery for young people, families and elderly residents. In doing so, the workshop sought to imagine futures where public spaces are not sites of exclusion, or competition, but everyday infrastructures of mutual support, intergenerational connection, and collective well-being.

A group of twelve participants from across academia, private and public with a very diverse expertise on the topic gathered to share views and discuss these questions, exploring the question of care and imagine care-full public space futures in Sweden. The workshop set to work on these objectives:

1. Continue exchanging and conversing within and beyond the Caring Cities (informally formed peer) Group on how Care Ethics can be used to inform urban governance and planning, with a special interest in the Swedish context.

2. Consider the practical implications of taking a care ethics perspective on public places in Sweden and reflect on how currently used classifications of public spaces in published literature (e.g. Carmona, 2010) capture Swedish specificities.

3. Facilitate exchanges across disciplinary and sectoral domains by creating space for meaningful discussions and exchanges between scholars from diverse fields, including planners, practitioners, and experts from various sectors.

4. Consider and discuss gaps in academic scholarship, as well as the needs that practitioners have in relation to public place governance. Exchange ideas on what are most urgent and relevant questions within the Ethics of Care and planning nexus.

2. Care and Public Space Introduction

The day commenced with [Dr Miriam Williams](#) providing an introductory talk on care and public space. Miriam defined how care has been approached in academic scholarship, providing the most common definition from Tronto (1993, p. 113) as

a "species activity that includes everything that we do to maintain, continue, and repair our 'world' so that we can live in it as well as possible". That world includes our bodies, our selves, and our environment, all of which we seek to interweave in a complex, life sustaining web."

Figure 1: Opening Talk by Miriam Williams

The universal need for care was emphasised and the multiple ways care has been applied as a focus of practitioners in the areas of valuing the work of carers and caring in care sectors and unpaid care work; caring for carers; gender and time policies; environmental care; and care as an organisational ethos were introduced.

Examples of care-informed policies from the most recent United Cities and Local Governments journal were introduced in a recent publication by Williams and Rodela (2025) accessible under open access at the Journal of Multimedia [here](#).

Miriam introduced the idea of public spaces as an infrastructure of care from the [Power of Public Spaces](#) research collaboration. Drawing on the work of [Carmona](#), Miriam introduced a typology of urban spaces for discussion later in the day.

3. Session 1: Exploring Ethics of Care in Urban Context

To facilitate dialogue and exchange among the participants during the day, we invited everyone to form mixed small groups and engage with a set of predefined questions used to guide the discussions. The first session focused on two questions as follows:

Question 1: How would you define care in planning and management of public spaces and places in Sweden?

Group 1 was composed of four senior academics and two practitioners, one of which of whom works at a public organization and the other at a private organization. The group reflected on the elements that con-

stitute care in the planning and management of public spaces and how these elements take shape in practice. This reflection led to the emergence of a definition of care within this group that was shaped by four core elements: **needs**, **localised interventions**, the **time** required to implement these interventions today, and the consideration of time as a factor in how planning interventions unfold over longer periods.

The group also reflected on the practical aspects of the planning profession as a public service, highlighting the challenges of planning for the diversity of social groups and consistently 'caring' for them. One point raised was that planners often struggle to stay closely connected to community needs, as these needs are dynamic and subject to change. This challenge is exacerbated when bureaucratic procedures and routines aimed at ensuring legal compliance take precedence. Additionally, the group discussed how at times there is a gap between the intended planning— e.g. a housing and playground area—and the outcomes once these interventions are completed. One example mentioned was the case of a housing project on a brown field in South Stockholm where apartments were built, but the planned community center was not completed.

Drawing on the current challenges related to safety and security in Swedish suburbs, group 1 considered how care is not always directed toward vulnerable group specifically (as are e.g. minors in gangs), but rather toward those who feel threatened by youth gangs. The group reflected on how, on one hand there has been an increase in police presence and safety measures on the streets in result to youth gang crimes. On the other hand, there have been also major funding cuts for sports and recreational activities for vulnerable youth, with some youth centers and schools closing in the

region. This situation is allegedly contributing to youth gathering on the streets, making them more susceptible to recruitment and gang involvement.

Group 2, made of one senior and four junior academics and two practitioners from the public and private sectors defined care in a range of ways and identified particular key themes shaping their understanding of care and public space including values; specific activities and activations; approaches to public space provisioning and design; governance; and challenges. **Values** that would shape caring public spaces include cultural diversity, inclusion, intergenerational, participatory, place-based, belonging and welcome. **Specific activities or activations** that have the potential to reflect these values include creating meeting places, service provision, providing groups for teens, elderly, parents and children. **Public Space provisioning and design** discussion centered on the provision of different types of public indoor and outdoor spaces including museums, libraries, community centers, facilities, movement spaces and playgrounds. It also involved a discussion of particular infrastructures that would be available to support the experience of the places as caring including water fountains, toilets, non-paid facilities, accessible facilities and the potential of using places like Schools

as public spaces when other indoor spaces were less available. Discussion on **governance** practices included the opportunity for including diverse groups to be involved in decision making and using particular assessments including gender mainstreaming, child impact assessments and other mechanisms. **Challenges** included safety and security, increasingly privatised public spaces, segregation of particular groups, experiences of public spaces as uncaring, often top-down planning practices, the exclusion of particular groups from participating in decision making and the challenges of weather (heat and cold) which impacts on which types of public spaces can be used when and how.

Question 2: What is missing from the shared typology (see: Carmona 2010) of public space in a Swedish perspective?

Group 1: The group started with a reflection on how privatisation in cities is currently pressing on public places in Sweden and how municipalities appear to be struggling with public space maintenance, and how this might be part of a broader trend in the political economy of Swedish cities.

Sätra Torg

5/14/2025

World Imagery

Low Resolution 15m Imagery

High Resolution 60cm Imagery

High Resolution 30cm Imagery

Citations

1:1 627
0 0.01 0.01 0.02 mi
0 0.01 0.02 0.04 km
Map data © Microsoft, SoHooz, Esri, TomTom, Garmin, FAO, NOAA, USGS, © OpenStreetMap contributors, and the GIS User Community

Figure 2: Sätra Torg

We took the example of public squares (in Swedish: *torg*) from urban districts in the periphery of Stockholm which were designed as a public space with benches and other siting elements, with some pieces of art and green infrastructure. Most commonly the *torg* (Figure 2) will be central and surrounded by a cluster, or a strip of low rising buildings meant for commercial activities (shop, barber, small retail, fast-food, etc). However, due to economic challenges municipalities faced with maintenance of that infrastructure some of them have subcontracted that to the private sector. This leads us to today to public squares managed by a private sector. And while squares are freely used as transit areas by citizens who need to pass by and access is free, the private sector has a major influence on uses that are more structured and might need a permit e.g. farmers market, festivals, organized gatherings, etc. This we identified to be a Swedish exception to a more generally understood idea of a square functioning as a public space.

Group 2: Participants were asked to reflect on the typology of Urban Space Types that was developed by Matthew Carmona (2010) and consider if there was anything missing from the Swedish perspective and experience. The typology is provided in Figure 3 below:

Key themes that emerged in response to this discussion were:

- The importance of temporal public spaces activations.
- Experiences of weather and light in creating new forms of spaces and shaping experiences of public spaces e.g. snow and long days or long nights due to seasonality.
- Questioning the appropriateness of the term “negative” or “positive” spaces.
- The role of the “right to roam” in Sweden shaping rights to occupy space.
- The existence of additional multifunctional spaces and other ways of using spaces.
- Growing number of town squares or public spaces that are privately owned, managed and cared for.
- Other types of spaces not included e.g. public saunas, swimming houses and abandoned spaces.

Additions to the typology from Group 2 can be found in Table 1 marked in red.

'Positive Spaces'	Natural/semi-natural urban space	Rivers, natural features, seafronts, canals	Ambiguous Spaces	Interchange space	Metros, bus interchanges, railway stations, bus/tram stops
	Civic space	Streets, squares, promenades		Public 'Private' space	Privately owned 'civic' space, business parks, church grounds
	Public open space	Parks, gardens, commons, urban forests, cemeteries		Conspicuous spaces'	Cul-de-sacs, dummy gated enclaves
'Negative Spaces'	Movement space	Main roads, motorways, railways, underpasses	Internalized 'public' space	Shopping/leisure malls, introspective megastructures	
	Service Spaces	Car parks, service yards	Retail Space	Shops, covered markets, petrol stations	
	Left over space	'SLOAP' (space left over after planning), modernist open space	Third spaces	Cafes, restaurants, libraries, town halls, religious buildings	
	Undefined space	Redevelopment spaces, abandoned space, transient space	Private 'public' space	Institutional grounds, housing estates, university campuses	
Private Spaces	Private open space	Urban agricultural remnants, private woodlands	Visible private space	Front gardens, allotments, gated squares	
	External private space	Gated streets /enclaves, private gardens, private sports clubs, parking courts	Interface space	Street cafes, private pavement space	
	Internal private space	Offices, houses etc.	User selecting space	Skateparks, playgrounds, sports fields/grounds/ courses	

Figure 3: A typology of Urban Spaces (text from Carmona, 2010).

Table 1: A Typology of Urban Space Types: the Swedish Experience

Public Spaces	Natural/semi-natural urban space	Rivers, natural features, seafronts, canals, lakes, ponds, blue infrastructures, quiet forests, wild spaces, consciously unplanned spaces
	Civic space	Streets, squares, promenades
	Public open space	Parks, gardens, commons, urban forests, cemeteries, quiet forests
	Movement space	Main roads, motorways, railways, underpasses, paths for walking and cycling
	Moving spaces	Play spaces on trains, markets on trains
	Temporary and permanent multifunctional mobility spaces	Smart roads, playful roads/streets, shared interactive streets and spaces, temporary activations e.g. Sommargator/ summer streets
Ambiguous Spaces	Interchange space	Metros, bus interchanges, railway stations, bus/tram stops
	Public 'Private' space	Privately owned 'civic' space, business parks, church grounds
	Conspicuous spaces'	Cul-de-sacs, dummy gated enclaves
	Internalized 'public' space	Shopping/leisure malls, introspective megastructures
	Retail Space	Shops, covered markets, petrol stations
	Third spaces	Cafes, restaurants, libraries, town halls, religious buildings, museums, saunas, swimming houses, community gardens
	Private 'public' space	Institutional grounds, housing estates, university campuses, town squares, playgrounds, open spaces in developments owned privately Torg.
	Visible private space	Front gardens, allotments, gated squares
	Interface space	Street cafes, private pavement space
	User selecting space	Skateparks, playgrounds, sports fields/grounds/courses
	Abandoned buildings	Squats, ruins
Right to roam	Potentially many private paddocks, fields can be used for walking and camping	
Private Spaces	External private space	Urban agricultural remnants, private woodland
	Internal private space	Gated streets /enclaves, private gardens, private sports clubs, parking courts
	Internal private space	Offices, houses etc.

SOURCE: Adapted from Carmona (2010)

4. Session 2: Exploring examples of place-making

Session Two asked groups to discuss and share examples of placemaking experiences in public spaces. Prompts for this activity included asking people to reflect on a particular example: where it was located; who owned and managed the space; who was involved in the place-making project; what the aim was; who the public space was for; the types of physical, material alterations that were made to the place; whether these changed; who used the place or how it was experienced; what were the barriers, enablers or constraints of the example were; and what can be learnt from this example about how public spaces design and management can become more care-full?

Group 1 discussed two different place-making interventions but each emerging to address a major social challenge that given urban area is facing. We discussed the [Seniortorget](#) (a meeting place for seniors) in Umeå which is a physical space serving as a community center for the elderly population who finds their support with use ICT and public digital services (Sweden has most of its public services digitalised), finds opportunity to socialise and recreate. The center serves as an important intervention in responding to the elderly loneliness epidemic and seeks to create community.

We also discussed an intervention meant for the Årsta-bro bridge connecting Årstaberg with Södermalm. Unfortunately, this site has been associated with suicides, and the authorities aimed to address this issue by modifying the built infrastructure, such as installing fencing to restrict access. Various interventions were considered (e.g., higher fences, rolling railings) and each had different costs. We discussed how a such a complex social problem cannot be properly addressed with build infrastructure alone but also acknowledged that it is very much needed. In such complex cases there is a need for many social actors to provide perspectives and share knowledge. During the conversation we also learnt that interventions which seek to preserve human life are in fact weighed against an economic check. We reflected on how such a process goes against a care-informed approach and agreed that it is also important to consider values that underpin policy-making by those who make important decisions of this kind.

From these reflections we concluded that: money is not enough, values that policy makers have shape interventions that will be supported; it is important to help policy makers learn from past experiences; it is relevant to have in place a system to evaluate how given

interventions performed and how well they served the intended purpose, or not. Lastly, this should be part of a policy-learning cycle and accountability.

Group 2 looked at examples of placemaking and brainstormed examples of both government-led and community-led place-making. We discussed the **Cleaning days** that are held in apartment buildings by neighbourhood apartment associations as examples of a community-led activities of maintenance and community connection where residents work together, share Fika and improve local public spaces. Challenges for this type of activity included engaging people who were renting to be involved.

Temporary activations or seasonal activations of public spaces including summer streets or Sommargator which involves temporary car free streets, café seating, playgrounds etc run by Stockholm Stad who involve local schools in participation. Particular examples of places were also discussed including Umeå where a range of different public space activations have occurred including:

- [Frizon](#), a place planned with young girls to hang out
- [Seniortorget](#): a central place for seniors to gather with a variety of activations
- [Mötesplats Stocke](#) a unique meeting place outside of Umeå that is a community-led facility and meeting place.
- Neighbourhood group markets, picnics and gatherings.

[Fritidsbanken](#) is also a leisure equipment library that has locations throughout Sweden. The ability of Umeå Kommun to engage with ideas of care has been connected to the political continuity of the region, civic engagement and involvement. Other examples mentioned included the activities occurring in **Fittja** which has involved the private sector, municipality and police planning spaces for safety but has been more of a Top-down approach. The challenge of participation fatigue was raised.

5. Session 3: Imagining Care-full Public Spaces Futures

Group 1: the group chose to use the [Seniortorget](#) as the place we continued to focus our discussion on to imagine how it could be transformed to become care-full in the future. The group talked about how such an approach should ideally be less about the physical ele-

ments and infrastructures that shape a place and more about the relationship that defines those who inhabit that space. So, we talked about how a community center for elderly that is welcoming to elderly who have different ethnic backgrounds and personal histories could come about. We identified respect of diversity, warmth and acceptance as key to building a care-full senior citizen center in the future. We discussed the value in deconstructing “normality” as an exercise of reparation and identification of norms that drive human action and shape communities we build together. There is value in making these norms visible and in reflecting on how such norms shaping our cities.

Life in advanced age is difficult, often marked by poor health or disease, for which reason elderly diets need to be lighter, more controlled, and may end up being not as tasty but instead dull. We considered how food is important and how consuming food together is an act of care and also an opportunity to meet each other’s ethnic culinary traditions. Food not only nourishes but can also unite people as an expression of care that is very much needed in a care-full future.

Group 2 worked together to identify one place that could be transformed to become care-full in the future. We identified particular values, physical infrastructures, social infrastructures and atmospheres and practices that the space would have. The public space is a well-known civic square in the center of Stockholm called “Sergels Torg”. At present there is little shade and not

many reasons for people to spend time in the public space. An important public facility, the Kulturhus adjoins the square and it is regularly used for protests. These reflections are listed in in Figure 4.

6. Conclusions and next steps

This workshop has focused on how an Ethics of Care can inform urban governance and the planning and management of public spaces. In a context where spatial segregation, densification, and reduced safety is increasingly shaping urban life in Sweden, grounding planning practices in relational, context-sensitive approaches is a relevant and needed perspective. As digital engagement and social isolation are very much shaping how people today relate to one another, the importance of fostering inclusive and supportive environments for young people, families, and elderly residents to gather and meet each other becomes even more significant.

Throughout the discussions, several promising examples of care-informed planning emerged. While these initiatives might not always be explicitly named as such, they nonetheless align with the ontological principles of an Ethics of Care, where relationality, interdependence, and attentiveness to human vulnerability are at the core. Notably, many existing interventions by Swedish municipalities already focus on vulnerable groups, particularly youth and the elderly, reflecting a recognition of their specific needs and the importance

Figure 4: Transforming Sergels Torg through design and practice. Source: Group 2, Map made using ARC GIS Online.

of fostering inclusive public spaces.

However, the discussions also revealed that there is substantial potential to deepen the integration of care into planning practices. One promising direction would be establishing systematic checks on how planning interventions affect well-being. Such an approach would ensure that care is not just a guiding principle but something that is more measurable in the way or the outcome it is able to generate by for instance being integrated into the entire lifecycle of urban projects.

The insights shared in the workshop speak about the need to cultivate planning practices that are more responsive and attentive to the lived realities of diverse social groups. While some initial steps have been taken, the journey toward genuinely care-informed planning is an ongoing process of challenging established practices and the ideas of whom are cities for (Rodela et al 2025; Williams and Rodela, 2025). There remains a wide range of opportunities for urban planners, policymakers, and researchers to engage with these ideas more fully and develop approaches that actively incorporate care into the urban fabric. As we continue researching contemporary challenges of modern urban life, advancing our understanding of how to use Ethics of Care to shape our cities is an important way forward for inclusive, compassionate and resilient urban environments.

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8. Appendix

Day Program

09:00 - 09:10 Welcome

09:10 - 09:30 Introductions

09:30 - 09:40 Care and Public Space by Dr. Miriam Williams

09:40 - 10:30 Session 1: Exploring Ethics of Care in Urban Context

10:30 - 10:45 Break

10:45 - 11:30 Session 2: Exploring examples of placemaking

11:00 - 11:45 Session 3: Imagining Care-full Public Spaces Futures

11:45 - 12:15 Wrap up of the Session

12:15 - 13:30 Lunch Break

List of Participants

1. Ann Mutvei, Södertörn University,
2. Anna Sandström Emmelin, Umeå Municipality
3. Gavin Nilsson Lewis , Linköping University
4. Jennie Björstad, AFRY
5. Madelenine Bonow, Södertörn University,
6. Malleel Abdullahi, Sweco
7. Miriam Williams, Macquarie University
8. Natasha Webster, Örebro University
9. Oldouz Nejadi, Södertörn University,
10. Rebecka Boström Gatti, Umeå Municipality
11. Romina Rodela, Södertörn University
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